

CASE REPORT**Exercise Stress Testing Induced Brugada Phenocopy**Selcuk Ozturk, MD^{ID}; Onur Akgun, MD^{ID}; Ozgur Ciftci, MD^{ID}**Summary**

Brugada syndrome (BrS) is an inherited channelopathy associated with ventricular tachyarrhythmias and sudden cardiac death in individuals with a structurally normal heart and Brugada electrocardiography (ECG) pattern and clinical history. BrS is categorized into three types according to ECG morphology, but the ECG of BrS may be intermittent, fluctuating, and occasionally concealed. Exercise is known to induce Brugada ECG phenocopy or mask ST-segment changes in BrS patients, depending on autonomic nervous system activity. Herein, we describe a case of a patient who developed type-1 Brugada ECG phenocopy and prominent bradycardia during the recovery phase of exercise stress testing.

Keywords: arrhythmia, Brugada electrocardiography pattern, Brugada syndrome, channelopathy, stress testing

Correspondance

Selcuk Ozturk, MD

selcukozturk85@hotmail.com

Department of Cardiology, Kirikkale University
Faculty of Medicine, Kirikkale, Turkey

Received: 9 May 2024

Accepted: 30 June 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13115932

Introduction

Brugada syndrome (BrS) is an inherited channelopathy associated with ventricular tachyarrhythmias and sudden cardiac death (SCD) in individuals with a structurally normal heart. The electrocardiography (ECG) of BrS is characterized by QRS morphology similar to right bundle branch block (RBBB) and ST-segment elevation in the right precordial leads. BrS is categorized into three types according to ECG morphology, but the ECG of BrS may be intermittent, fluctuating, and occasionally concealed, which can present a diagnostic and therapeutic dilemma. Moreover, the BrS ECG

pattern, or Brugada phenocopy, can be provoked by various pharmacological agents or conditions such as fever, electrolyte disturbances, alcohol and cocaine intoxication, and physical activity. Exercise is known to induce Brugada ECG phenocopy or mask ST-segment changes in BrS patients, depending on autonomic nervous system activity.¹⁻³ Herein, we describe a case of a patient with a normal baseline ECG who developed a type-1 BrS ECG phenocopy and prominent bradycardia during the recovery phase of exercise stress testing (EST) and discuss possible pathogenetic mechanisms in light of the existing literature.

Case Report

A 38-year-old Caucasian male patient was admitted to the cardiology outpatient clinic with the complaint of atypical chest pain. He had a history of diabetes mellitus and hyperlipidemia, treated with metformin and atorvastatin. He had no history of smoking, alcohol or drug abuse, and no family history of SCD or cardiovascular disease. He denied dyspnea, palpitations, syncope, and presyncope. Physical examination and blood tests were all within normal limits. The 12 - lead ECG showed normal sinus rhythm with T-wave inversion in lead V1 (Figure 1). Transthoracic echocardiography demonstrated normal systolic and diastolic functions without significant valvular pathology.

The patient then underwent exercise stress testing

Figure 1. The baseline 12-lead electrocardiogram of the patient demonstrates a normal sinus rhythm with accompanying T wave inversion in lead V1.

Figure 2. **A.** Electrocardiography obtained in the supine position before exercise stress testing showed RBBB and T wave inversion in V1-3 leads without prominent ST-segment elevation. **B.** Coved-type ST-segment elevations accompanying RBBB in V1-3 leads developed at peak exercise, suggestive of a type-1 Brugada phenocopy. **C.** During the early phase of recovery, significant bradycardia at a heart rate of 30 bpm developed, in addition to classical type-1 Brugada phenocopy on ECG, and the patient reported dizziness. **D.** Bradycardia resolved spontaneously within 10 seconds.

Figure 3. A. The baseline 12-lead ECG showed a normal sinus rhythm with T wave inversion in lead V1. B. The 12-lead ECG obtained from the upper intercostal space demonstrated a right bundle branch block pattern and ST-segment elevation in lead V1.

Table 1. Case reports of patients associated with Brugada Syndrome or phenocopy and Exercise Stress Testing

Authors	Age / Gender	Admission symptom	Baseline ECG	Exercise ECG findings
Jacky Kit Chan ²	55 / M	Exercise syncope	Mild early repolarization in anterior leads	- Augmentation of ST-segment elevation and polymorphic non-sustained VT in recovery phase
Cho <i>et al.</i> ³	42 / M	Chest discomfort after meals	Normal	- Coved type ST-segment elevation in V ₁₋₂ during the effort phase with no reciprocal changes - Normalization of ST-segment during the recovery phase
Batra <i>et al.</i> ⁴	18 / M	Exercise syncope	Type-1 Brugada pattern	- Wide complex tachycardia consistent with VT
Aboyme <i>et al.</i> ⁵	24 / M	Chest pain	Type-2 Brugada pattern	- During peak exercise type-1 Brugada pattern - During recovery phase type-2 Brugada pattern
Papadakis <i>et al.</i> ⁶	36 / M	Asymptomatic	Minor ST-segment elevation in V ₁ and 0.2 mV saddle-shaped ST-segment elevation in V ₂	- 0.7 mV ST-segment elevation with coved pattern and T wave inversion in V ₂ and ST-segment elevation and T wave inversion in V ₃ at peak exertion and ST-segment elevation in leads V ₁₋₃ post-exercise - Multiple ventricular extrasystoles in recovery phase that terminated spontaneously and ST-segment elevation in leads V ₁₋₃ post-exercise
Archontakis <i>et al.</i> ⁷	43 / M	Asymptomatic	Incomplete RBBB and slight ST-segment elevation in V ₁	- Type-1 Brugada pattern in the sixth minute of recovery phase and normalization in a few minutes
Jayasuriya <i>et al.</i> ⁸	34 / M	Atypical chest pain	No evidence of Brugada pattern	- ST-segment elevation in V ₂₋₃ at pretest standing ECG - Recovery of ST-segment elevation during the first minute of exercise - ST-segment elevation in V ₁₋₂ at peak exercise - Transient type-1 Brugada pattern and normalization during recovery phase
Ozeke <i>et al.</i> ⁹	59 / M	Cardiac evaluation before urological surgery	Incomplete RBBB with saddleback type ST-segment elevation in leads V ₁₋₂ and left axis deviation	- VT with a LBBB pattern and saddleback type ST-segment elevation in V ₂ - Coved type ST-segment elevation in V ₂ in the recovery phase

Grimster <i>et al.</i> ¹⁰	33 / M	Acute asthma	Type-2 Brugada pattern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - T wave inversion in V₂ and reduction in ST-segment elevation in V₃ during 13th minute of exercise - A drop in blood pressure associated with dizziness consistent with a vasovagal episode on cessation of exercise - Type-1 Brugada pattern during recovery phase
Esperer <i>et al.</i> ¹¹	30 / M	Light-headedness and syncope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type-1 Brugada pattern - Slight saddleback type ST-segment elevation in V₁ in an earlier ECG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease at JWA in V₁₋₃ progressively with increasing workload and increase during recovery phase
Garcia-Borbolla <i>et al.</i> ¹²	38 / M	Chest pain	Type-1 Brugada pattern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustained monomorphic VT with RBBB morphology after 1 minute of recovery phase
Guevara-Valdivia <i>et al.</i> ¹³	38 / M	Syncope	BrS pattern with saddleback variety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ST-segment elevation in V₁₋₂ during the effort phase and at maximum effort - Normalization of ST-segment elevation during the recovery phase
Guevara-Valdivia <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴	28 / M	Syncope	RBBB and ST-segment elevation in the right precordial leads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Normalization of ST-segment elevation in V₂ during exercise - ST-segment elevation in the right precordial leads post-exercise
Raposeiras-Roubin <i>et al.</i> ¹⁵	61 / F	Chest pain	Type-1 Brugada pattern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Normalization of ST-segment elevation during exercise - ST-segment elevation during recovery phase characteristic of type-1 Brugada pattern
Mok <i>et al.</i> ¹⁶	54 / M	Palpitation and pre-syncope following physical exertion	Sustained monomorphic VT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-sustained VT - BrS was diagnosed after flecainide provocation test
Bertaglia <i>et al.</i> ¹⁷	54 / F	Asymptomatic	Incomplete RBBB, coved type ST-segment elevation and the inversion of T waves in leads V ₁₋₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Normal exercise test
Goto <i>et al.</i> ¹⁸	41 / M	Palpitation	Normal sinus rhythm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monomorphic VT with LBBB that spontaneously terminated after exercise and coved type ST-segment elevation in leads V₁₋₂

				-Normalization of ST-segment elevation during post-exercise recovery phase
Garcia-Fuertes <i>et al.</i> ¹⁹	19 / M	Atypical chest pain	Type-3 Brugada pattern	- Type-1 Brugada pattern during recovery phase
Tijskens <i>et al.</i> ²⁰	52 / M	Asymptomatic	Bifascicular block (RBBB and LAFB)	- Type-1 Brugada pattern during maximal exercise and disappearance immediately after cessation of exercise
Ströker <i>et al.</i> ²¹	49 / M	Exercise presyncope	Episodes of non-sustained VT in ICD memory	-Type-1 Brugada pattern at peak exercise and accompanying several ventricular ectopic beats in recovery phase - Masking and unmasking of Type-1 Brugada pattern with forced expiratory effort and rebreathing normally
Enriquez <i>et al.</i> ²²	76 / M	Atypical chest pain	Evidence of inferior necrosis	- ST-segment elevation in leads V ₁₋₃ with a coved appearance and negative T waves in the 4 th minute of exercise - Normalization of ST-segment elevation over a period of 3 minutes after stopping the test
Safabakhsh <i>et al.</i> ²³	46 / M	Symptomatic atrial arrhythmia	Early repolarization in the anterior precordial leads suspicious for type-2 Brugada pattern	- Type-1 Brugada pattern most evident at high heart rates that resolved in recovery phase during flecainide treatment
Zou <i>et al.</i> ²⁴	50 / M	Palpitation and presyncope during physical exertion	Sinus rhythm with incomplete RBBB	- Type-1 Brugada pattern in the 3 th minute of recovery which normalized in the 5 th minute and accompanying multifocal PVCs and three beats of monomorphic VTs
Yuasa <i>et al.</i> ²⁵	33 / M	Palpitation	Normal sinus rhythm	- PVCs developed toward peak exercise and were soon followed by monomorphic VT with RBBB and superior axis - J-point elevation during exercise and normalization during post-exercise recovery

Abbreviations: BrS, Brugada syndrome; ECG, electrocardiography; F, female; ICD, implantable cardioverter defibrillator; JWA, J-wave amplitude; LAFB, Left anterior fascicular block; LBBB, left bundle branch block; M, male; mV, millivolt; PVC, premature ventricular complex; RBBB, right bundle branch block; VT, ventricular tachycardia.

(EST) using the Bruce treadmill protocol. He completed the test with no symptoms at 6 minutes and 48 seconds, achieving 91% of the target heart rate and 11.1 metabolic equivalents. The pretest ECG obtained in the supine position showed RBBB and T-wave inversion in leads V1-3, without prominent ST-segment elevation. At peak exercise, coved-type ST-segment elevations developed in leads V1-3, suggestive of a type-1 Brugada phenocopy. During the early recovery phase, significant bradycardia, with a heart rate of 30 beats per minute, developed along with the classical type-1 Brugada phenocopy on ECG, and the patient reported dizziness. The bradycardia resolved spontaneously within 10 seconds (Figure 2A-D).

Afterwards, basal and upper intercostal space 12-lead ECG recordings in the supine position were performed to confirm the Brugada phenocopy pattern (Figure 3A-B). Subsequent diagnostic workup, including ambulatory rhythm Holter monitoring, coronary angiography, and electrophysiological study, were all within normal limits. A provocative drug challenge test and cardiac magnetic resonance imaging were recommended, but the patient refused further testing. Thus, conservative management, including lifestyle changes and education with close follow-up, was planned. He has been asymptomatic and has not experienced any cardiac events for one year.

Discussion

Brugada syndrome (BrS) was initially described in 1992, and our understanding of its genotypic and phenotypic principles, as well as clinical and therapeutic management, continues to evolve. Due to the asymptomatic nature and concealed or transient ECG pattern of the disease, the true prevalence of BrS is difficult to assess. Moreover, various conditions such as fever, electrolyte disturbances, alcohol and cocaine intoxication, and physical activity can induce the BrS ECG pattern in the absence of a clinical history, known as Brugada phenocopy. Thus, it is not surprising that many patients are diagnosed incidentally during or after an exercise stress test (EST). On the other hand, EST might induce arrhythmias in an asymptomatic or yet undiagnosed BrS patient.¹⁻³

Limited data exists about exercise stress testing (EST) in Brugada syndrome (BrS) or Brugada

phenocopy, and the current literature mostly consists of case reports involving patients with diverse clinical conditions (Table 1).⁴⁻²⁵ Generally, exercise is known to decrease typical coved-type ST-segment elevations due to increased sympathetic activity, which raises the heart rate. In contrast, ST-segment elevation often increases during the recovery phase due to heightened vagal activity through activation of the parasympathetic nervous system. This is why arrhythmias and SCD in BrS patients occasionally occur during sleep and/or rest periods and are often associated with bradycardia.^{1,3} However, some reports indicate augmentation of the ST-segment during exercise and normalization during recovery.^{3,13,18,20,22,23,25} The mechanistic basis for this paradoxical response is not well understood but may relate to differences in autonomic nervous system modulation and/or specific genetic mutations in patients. For instance, a specific SCN5A mutation involving the C-terminal portion of the sodium channel has been suggested to be associated with a heart rate-dependent ECG phenotype, specifically ST-segment augmentation, in BrS patients.²⁶

In our patient, the pretest ECG obtained in the supine position did not show prominent ST-segment elevation. However, coved-type ST-segment elevations with RBBB in the right precordial leads suggestive of Brugada phenocopy developed at peak exercise. The classical type-1 Brugada phenocopy pattern with significant bradycardia occurred on ECG during the early phase of the recovery period. The ECG changes observed in our patient may be mutation-specific, but we could not perform genetic testing due to unavailability. A provocative drug challenge test was recommended to the patient, as well as cardiac magnetic resonance imaging, due to the possibility that some cases of arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia can overlap with BrS. However, the patient refused further testing.

Exercise stress testing is not part of routine screening for the diagnosis and follow-up of BrS. However, it has been suggested for prognostication of BrS patients. For example, ST-segment augmentation during the recovery phase of EST was found to be associated with adverse cardiac events in BrS patients in a previous study.²⁷ Moreover, various electrocardiographic alterations during EST, such as an increase in S wave upslope duration ratio >30% at peak exercise, augmentation of J-point elevation in lead aVR >2 mm in late recovery, and delayed heart

rate recovery, have been identified as independent predictors of arrhythmic events in asymptomatic BrS patients.²⁸ Additionally, EST may provoke clinically significant or lethal arrhythmias linked with BrS, such as ventricular tachycardia.^{4,9,12,16,18,24,25}

In our patient, significant bradycardia accompanied by a classical type-1 Brugada phenocopy pattern developed on the ECG during the early recovery phase of EST, and the patient reported dizziness. However, both the bradycardia and dizziness resolved quickly. We believe that the bradycardia resulted from increased vagal activity. Furthermore, ambulatory rhythm Holter monitoring and electrophysiological studies did not reveal any significant arrhythmias. Consequently, we decided to follow up with the patient conservatively and diagnosed the condition as exercise-induced Brugada phenocopy rather than BrS, due to the absence of arrhythmic history, family history, genetic testing, provocative drug challenge testing, and normal electrophysiological studies.

In conclusion, exercise stress testing (EST) might be beneficial in Brugada syndrome (BrS) for unmasking ECG alterations and arrhythmias, particularly in undiagnosed and/or asymptomatic patients. The occurrence of Brugada phenocopies during EST is a rare phenomenon that warrants further investigation in future studies.

Informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for the publication of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interests

None

Funding

The authors state that the current study received no financial support.

References

1. Masrur S, Memon S, Thompson PD. Brugada syndrome, exercise, and exercise testing. *Clin Cardiol.* 2015;38:323-326.
2. Chan K. Roles of exercise treadmill test in the diagnosis & risk stratification of cardiac channelopathies. *J Hk Coll Cardiol.* 2023;29(5):171-179.
3. Cho JH, Cho D-K, Choi JY, et al. An unusual case of exercise-induced idiopathic Brugada electrocardiographic pattern. *Korean Circulation J.* 2007;37:517-519.
4. Batra AS, Watson R, McCanta AC. Exercise-induced syncope and Brugada syndrome. *Ann Pediatr Cardiol.* 2019;12(3):292-294.
5. Aboyme A, Coromilas J, Scheinman M, et al. Exercise Induced Brugada Syndrome Type I Pattern. *HeartRhythm Case Rep.* 2022;8(4):288-291.
6. Papadakis M, Petzer E, Sharma S. Unmasking of the Brugada phenotype during exercise testing and its association with ventricular arrhythmia on the recovery phase. *Heart.* 2009;95(24):2022.
7. Archontakis S, Gatzoulis K, Arsenos P, et al. A case of asymptomatic Brugada electrocardiographic pattern incidentally unmasked during the recovery phase of an exercise stress test. *Hospital Chronicles.* 2011;6(4):200-202.
8. Jayasuriya C, Whitman M. Exercise-induced Brugada sign. *Europace.* 2011;13(3):446-447.
9. Ozeke O, Cagli K, Aras D, et al. Exercise-induced ventricular tachycardia associated with asymptomatic Brugada syndrome in a patient with urinary bladder stone. *Turk Kardiyol Dern Ars.* 2009;37(2):128-131.
10. Grimster A, Segal OR, Behr ER. Type I Brugada electrocardiogram pattern during the recovery phase of exercise testing. *Europace.* 2008;10(7):897-898.
11. Esperer HD, Hoos O, Hottenrott K. Syncope due to Brugada syndrome in a young athlete. *Br J Sports Med.* 2007;41(3):180-181.
12. García-Borbolla M, García-Borbolla R, Valenzuela LF, et al. Ventricular tachycardia induced by exercise testing in a patient with Brugada syndrome. *Rev Esp Cardiol.* 2007;60(9): 993-994.

13. Guevara-Valdivia ME, de Micheli A, Iturralde P, et al. Infrequent electrocardiographic changes during exercise stress test in a patient with Brugada's syndrome. *Arch Cardiol Mex.* 2003;73(3):212-217.
14. Guevara-Valdivia ME, Torres PI, de Micheli A, et al. Electrocardiographic changes during stress test in a patient with " Brugada syndrome". *Arch Cardiol.* 2001;71(1):66-72.
15. Raposeiras-Roubin S, Barreiro-Pardal C, Virgos-Lamela A, et al. Electrocardiographic changes during stress test in a patient with a type 1 Brugada electrocardiogram pattern: a curiosity with a clinical implication. *Rev Esp Anestesiología Reanim.* 2013;60(6): 352-353.
16. Mok NS, Chan NY. Brugada syndrome presenting with sustained monomorphic ventricular tachycardia. *Int J Cardiol.* 2004;97(2):307-309.
17. Bertaglia E, Michieletto M, Spedicato L, et al. Right bundle branch block, intermittent ST segment elevation and inducible ventricular tachycardia in an asymptomatic patient: an unusual presentation of the Brugada syndrome? *G Ital Cardiol.* 1998;28(8):893-898.
18. Goto M, Sato M, Kitazawa H, et al. Brugada syndrome combined with monomorphic ventricular tachycardia and atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia. *Intern Med.* 2015;54(10):1223-1226.
19. García-Fuertes D, Villanueva-Fernández E, Crespín-Crespín M, et al. Type 1 Brugada pattern unmasked during the recovery period of an exercise stress test. *Arq Bras Cardiol.* 2016;106(5):447-449.
20. Tijsskens M, Heidbuchel H, Sarkozy A. Supranormal heart rate during peak exercise stress test triggering type-1 Brugada ECG pattern. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol.* 2019;30(8):1367-1368.
21. Ströker E, de Asmundis C, Chierchia G-B, et al. Exercise-related Brugada pattern and monomorphic ventricular tachycardia in a patient with Brugada syndrome: interplay between body temperature, haemodynamics and vagal activity. *Eur Heart J.* 2016;37(7):655.
22. Enriquez A, Brugada J, Baranchuk A. Exercise-Induced Brugada Phenocopy. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol.* 2016;27(3):360-361.
23. Safabakhsh S, Krahn AD, Laksman Z. Exercise Testing With Flecainide Demonstrates Provocable Brugada Syndrome. *CJC Open.* 2021;3(8):1079-1081.
24. Zou G, Khanna M, Zahid S, et al. Ventricular fibrillation arrest due to Brugada syndrome in a coronavirus disease 2019 patient with negative procainamide challenge: a case report. *Eur Heart J Case Rep.* 2021;5(12):ytab454.
25. Yuasa S, Sato M, Kitazawa H, et al. Brugada syndrome and idiopathic left ventricular tachycardia unmasked by exercise and a class Ic drug. *J Electrocardiol.* 2014;47(5):721-724.
26. Veldkamp MW, Viswanathan PC, Bezzina C, et al. Two distinct congenital arrhythmias evoked by a multidysfunctional Na(+) channel. *Circ Res.* 2000;86(9):E91-E97.
27. Makimoto H, Nakagawa E, Takaki H, et al. Augmented ST-segment elevation during recovery from exercise predicts cardiac events in patients with Brugada syndrome. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2010;56(19):1576-1584.
28. Subramanian M, Prabhu MA, Harikrishnan MS, et al. The utility of exercise testing in risk stratification of asymptomatic patients with type 1 Brugada pattern. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol.* 2017;28(6):677-683.